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Transcript

Speaker 1

Hello, thank you for agreeing to be part of this interview. My name is Anna Makarudze. I'm currently pursuing a Masters in Software Engineering at the Plekhian Institute of Technology in Sweden. And my research is centered on vulnerabilities in open source dependencies. And I'm looking at this from a developer's perspective. And the motivation behind this topic is because of the rise in supply chain attacks that are happening to in organizations due to open source. So just a few ethical issues, participation in this interview is voluntary and you can withdraw at any time. You can decide to answer, just keep some questions if you're not comfortable answering them. And we will not retain any personal data that will make you identifiable. In example, you are going to be anonymous and I'll be recording this interview for the sake of verifying authenticity of the data that I present to my supervisor. The data will not be shared with any other parties except them.

And after the end of the research, the data will be deleted. So that's. We'll start by you introducing yourself in the project that you are either a developer from or a contributor or maintainer. And you can also tell me maybe about your job role and your background in the software development industry, how many years of experience you have. And also, which framework you are using between with five ecosystems, Python, Java, JavaScript, Ruby and HP, and then the web frameworks we are using for one framework for which is Django from the Python, then Spring Boot, Laravel, Next.js,

So you can mention all other projects that are related to the web framework that you may be maintaining outside the main framework. So you can start.

Speaker 2

Okay. Thank you, Anna.

I am working primarily in, actually, all my experience kind of for open source kind of comes from Python and the Django web framework.

My current role is a mentor/consultant. Before that, I've had about 12 years of experience, no, 14 years of experience using Django and Python, worked as a freelance consultant for a while, building out web apps, APIs and stuff.

And then there was a good three years full-time plus time before that as one of my clients working with them, doing education analytics. I think that's pretty much it.

My current roles are, I'm on the Django Steering Council. I'm an admin for Django Commons, which is an organization that seeks to help maintainers maintain open source software, which seems kind of relevant to what we're discussing here in the open source, sorry, supply chain attacks.

So I'm very interested in the results from that regard. I'm an admin for Djangonaut space, which helps onboard new contributors, and then I help maintain a couple packages like the Django debug toolbar and Django simple history. Yeah, I think that's pretty much it.

Speaker 1

Thank you. Do you, other than being part of the steering council, do you have any other roles that you attain to the Django framework, maybe example, trading issues, reviewing pull requests and whatnot?

Speaker 2

So not with the Django framework directly. I do maintain, help maintain, I'm like one of the two, or one of the couple core maintainers to the Django debug toolbar, which is a very popular third-party project. There we do, I help with everything of triaging issues, reviewing pull requests, writing code, merging it, doing releases, setting up CI, managing the project itself.

We actually just started acquiring funding from other sources and then it kind of routes through my bank account and it goes back to the DSF. Another role that is somewhat similar, but a little bit different is Django Commons. So that is an organization that seeks to house community open source projects.

So when a project creator gets to the point of like they want to transfer the project to somebody else, but they want to give it to the Django community, that's where Django Commons exists. It has a backstop of a group of individuals that oversee things without taking action.

It's just more of if something were to happen to one of the maintainers, the community still has the ability to pass that project off to another person. So it helps eliminate the lottery factor, the bus factor, whatever people prefer to call it.

Yeah, there's those aspects. And then with Django, it's more of, I don't, I write some code for Django. I do a few PR, like pull request reviews, but we're talking like maybe two PRs a year. So it's pretty infrequent.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. Okay, in terms of the packages that you maintain, for example, Django debug toolbar, are there any governance structures within your project may be responsible for security or anyone, anyone to be taken?

Speaker 2

Not for the toolbar. We are too small for that. So there are two of us that really cut the releases. And like if we had a security issue, we would be the first two to look at it. We would potentially raise it up. Well, I'm on the Django Commons admins team, so we haven't really gone through this exercise yet, but I would likely relay it to the other admins so that they're aware of it. But yeah, there's no formal structure there.

Speaker 1

All right. Okay, in terms of dependencies that you use in the projects, are there any dependencies that you get maybe from other ecosystems, maybe JavaScript or Ruby, or you only depend on Python and PyPi dependencies?

Speaker 2

No, I think, yeah, everything is dependent on the Python. But with the toolbar, we've been pretty explicit about trying to keep everything written within the project and not having to rely on an outside ecosystem.

We do have a couple of libraries, Python libraries, like what you mentioned of Python and PyPI, like SQL parse, and I think there's another one. But yeah, other than that, no, there's no-- we don't use a CSS framework.

We don't have a JavaScript framework that's built on top of it. Everything is-- it's all Python. We try to keep the number of dependencies very low for this particular project.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. And then how are security issues reported or managed within the project?

Speaker 2

These, we, for the debug toolbar, we follow Django Commons, which is using GitHub security advisories. I think that's what it's called. It has not, we've only had one security report that came through And that was back when the project was a part of Jazz Band.

And so I think that was like a private disclosure to the person who runs Jazz Band.

And then he forwarded it to the other maintainer and I, and I think we set it up on GitHub's private vulnerability branches, or I forget what they're always called. Yeah, it seemed to work well enough.

We haven't had any other like bugs reported as security issues. So yeah, it's not something that happens frequently enough where we can have a tried and true process for it.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. Okay, how conscious are you of the dangers that vulnerabilities dependencies present to your projects?

Speaker 2

More lately, I think early on in my career, it definitely wasn't a thought. Yeah, I think adding dependencies definitely has a different feel to it. I also just struggle in general with Python sometimes of if you pip install anybody's package and you do an import from there, like they can run whatever they want in like Python's dynamic nature, but you can monkey patch everything. It is a large amount of leeway we give people.

So I've been more and more concerned, but not taking a bunch of action. It's more of I just keep an eye on what Seth Larson is posting about in writing and seeing what practices I need to implement.

Speaker 1

Sorry, did you quote someone? Who are you writing something about?

Speaker 2

I was just saying Seth Larson, the Python, the PSF security. Yeah.

So he's somebody I respect a lot. And if he's starting to raise alarms on certain things, then I'm like, all right, I need to go look at that.

Speaker 1

All right. I'll take him out after the interview.

Speaker 2

OK.

Speaker 1

All right. How aware are you of supply chain attacks and their effects on projects in general?

Speaker 2

It's hard to answer that because I don't know what it's being compared against. I would say it's moderately aware. It's not something I'm going out and researching or looking for, but it is something, like I've got my...sort of social circles set up where if there is something that's happening that is large scale, I'll find out about it pretty quickly.

So I now that I think about it, I don't I don't think that's really the best way of going about it. Like there should be a better way of having that reported back up to me. But yeah, that's that's my answer. Inadequate answer.

Speaker 1

No, it's your answer. I'm not yet to measure the adequacy, but it's your answer. And then how do you identify dependents with vulnerabilities within your projects?

Speaker 2

How do I find that right, entities?

Speaker 1

With-- What tools do you use maybe?

Speaker 2

We would likely use Dependabot or PyPI, like the package managers to alert us to it as things get installed or package versions get yanked. But yeah, a lot of it's just relying on Dependabot giving us a heads up to it. I think we also offload some of that to the end developer because We don't, we just require the dependency to be installed, but it's not like we require very specific versions. I don't know how often we pin stuff. So a lot of times I think that falls to the actual project developers to deal with. Right.

Speaker 1

And suppose there is a vulnerable, okay, what influences the decision to update to newer patients of dependencies within your project?

00:13:18 Speaker 2

Primarily, it is if there's a minor or patch update, you can just update them as you go. If it's a larger update, making sure that CI runs, checking the release notes, determining if there are any backwards incompatibilities, doing, yeah the typical testing of making sure that the project's going to be functioning properly with it.

We don't, like the toolbar just doesn't have a ton of dependencies. I think it's probably like three, I really hope it's three dependencies. So they're pretty stable, but I guess, yeah, there isn't a ton of review that goes into like checking all the code that goes into each one of those version changes.

Speaker 1

All right. And how do you check the maintaining of dependencies in your projects? I know you already took that about Django Commons taking over projects that the developers are no longer maintaining. So do you keep check whether the dependencies that you are using, even if it's not Django debug tool by instance made for other projects. How do you keep check to see whatever you're using is still being mandated?

Speaker 2

That is a really good question. It depends on what, if I'm adding a new dependency, yes, I absolutely will go check the project's source code and see who's maintaining it, how often they've been adding changes.

Is it active? Is it How quickly are they releasing new versions when... So most of my projects are all Django based. It's a third-party project. When was the last time they released the latest version of support for Django? Is it six months later? Is it nine months later? That's a pretty good sign of whether or not something's well maintained. Checking to see what the issue count is, the PR count.

That's...I think that's primarily it. Like, does the project look active? I would probably say my gut would be like six to nine months. Like if there's activity within there, if I don't see it in a year or so, like I'll start to go look for those issues that people create of like, is this maintained or not? And then trying to get a sense of is the maintainer responding to stuff?

Is the maintainer just absent entirely. And then I'll usually have to make a judgment of how badly do I want that code? Can I just pull a piece of it out or do I just need to take it on with understanding that I'm going to go ahead and support it?

Yeah, I think that's probably depending on what, yeah, I think of the other part that would factor into it is like what kind of application am I building? Like what is the impact? Like in

my head, it's always something small of, hey, this is going to be used by a couple hundred people, that's not a huge impact.

But if it's something that has financial implications or health care implications, yeah, that then changes the calculus again of where does that risk analysis come along. Yeah.

Speaker 1

You mentioned the number of issues and pull requests. Does the number of issues, okay, I want to understand the criteria which use number of issues and pull requests to make a decision to see whether it is being maintained. Does it mean if the package has too many issues, it's being active or active maintained or unactive maintained?

Speaker 2

It could go both ways, I guess, of if a project only has a total of 50 issues ever, I'd be like, this probably isn't is this really super, is this really well maintained? Are people even using this? I guess it's really not a question of maintenance. It's more of a question of robustness.

Speaker 1

Robustness.

Speaker 2

Yeah. The too high of an issue count. Yeah, I think I'd be okay with a high issue count, but it definitely factors into level of maintenance because it probably would speak to, hey, this software is really complex and there's a lot going on and the maintainers don't have a full grasp of everything and aren't able to keep up with clearing technical debt or implementing, I don't wanna say implementing new features, but yeah, just maintaining the package.

Like I've seen it of at least one other library that's super complex. And yeah, the issue count there is pretty staggering.

Speaker 1

All right. And how do you handle like vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

Speaker 2

So is this within my own web applications using Django or within other open source projects like libraries? It's open. So if it's a vulnerability in an open source library, like then it becomes a bigger issue of who do we all have to disclose, like other packages that are

built on top of it, making sure that they're aware of it and that they can go through their own process of determining what level of disclosure is needed.

With the debug toolbar, we don't have a standard practice of or process of how to disclose things, or like what level, we'd probably end up relying, going to take a look at how Django does it. They've got some pretty robust set of security disclosures and taking a look at there and seeing if there's something there that we could re-implement. Within my own projects, yeah, it's elevating, determining like what the impact of it is gathering the information just so that whoever the stakeholders are, that they can make a determination of like, how do we move forward?

That's usually my first step. And then immediate remediation, maybe that'll happen before that if it's clearly something horrible and I need to like roll back stuff or yank something or, yeah. And then I work with the stakeholders to determine like, hey, this is how we should move something forward and yep, make the plan and execute it.

Speaker 1

OK, what remediation plans would you would you do, depending maybe on level of risk with the vulnerability?

Speaker 2

Could you ask that one more time, please?

Speaker 1

I'm saying you said you discussed with you discussed with that is to do what remediation you can do. So I'm asking the kinds of remediation that you can do without ordinary.

Speaker 2

It would be. I'm trying to go through and find an example.

Speaker 1

Okay, maybe do you update? Do you replace it? Do you?

Speaker 2

Oh. So yeah, with the security vulnerability we have at the toolbar, we yanked the, well, I think we, did we yank that release? I think we did. It went, I know we worked on it in private for about three months. I think the reporter said like, hey, standard is 90 days before there's a public disclosure.

So you have to try to have it fixed before then. And we're like, okay, like that seems fine. But the problem wasn't super difficult. And the reporter helped us work through it, like the solution. I don't, yeah, I don't know if we yanked it until we had a fix. I think it was one of those situations where we implemented the fix, yanked the release, then released the new version in Disklin, and then created the GitHub security advisory and alerted people to like, hey, there was a, a SQL injection. So that's how we did with the toolbar. In my head, I was going more of personal projects of-- OK.

00:22:21 Speaker 1

In your personal project, suppose this is a dependence that you maintain. Suppose it is somebody else's dependence that they maintain, then how will the remediation steps be like?

00:22:37 Speaker 2

So my understanding-- Yes. So I read through the security issue, figure out like where the vulnerability exists and determining like, is there overlap with my project? Like was I using that certain feature or was I not? And then determining from there of, okay, what is the impact on my users or my stakeholders? And yeah, going through the process of impact and how do you resolve this? How do you mitigate it?

And then either-- yeah, rolling back changes or rolling forward changes could be switching out the dependency version. It could be re-implementing some of the code on our own and trying to remove the dependency altogether. Yeah, it's usually going to depend on what exactly it is, for me at least.

Speaker 1

It's what we're asking about for you.

Speaker 2

Right. Yeah. Well, I mean, I know some other people probably organizations, large organizations probably have a very standard like, hey, here's the playbook. And for me, it's more of, I don't have a playbook. It's more, yeah, just on the fly.

Speaker 1

All right. Thank you. All right. You mentioned Django Commons. Okay, I want to understand the process of how do you take over projects that are no longer being maintained to maintainers come to you?

Speaker 2

So this is actually something we're trying to sort out right now. We don't have a good answer for it yet. We're trying. We're having. When projects come into Django Commons, we have a requirement that there is at least one person that is taking it over to be the maintainer. So every project that comes into Django Commons has active maintainers. Where we're struggling now is like just because they start with maintainers doesn't mean they're always going to have maintainers like the whole. So yeah, we don't have a solution, excuse me, written up for how to determine when a package is no longer maintained and what to do in those situations. We are likely, we're going through this right now of there's somebody, we have a package that a maintainer is not responding to issues as quickly as some users would like.

And they're not communicating in other ways, like through back channels. So it's really difficult to determine what level of support they need or want or what is going on. So we're trying to figure out, is this acceptable to the community? Is this acceptable just for this person's offered to be the maintainer? So like, that's just how they maintain software. Like that's, you get what you pay for. But there's also this ask or question of,

If they go completely silent for how long, when does that become, quote unquote, unmaintained software? And then we have an obligation to step in and help facilitate finding a new maintainer. Yeah, which then becomes a process of evaluating trust with somebody new. And so we are in the process of implementing that.

Speaker 1

Okay, thank you. So if any of the projects that you work with ever been exposed to supply chain attacks or is this something that you hear about?

Speaker 2

Yes, I think so. I know at my past job it was no, we used one of SolarWinds had their vulnerability a couple of years ago and we were using a different product of theirs. So we weren't exposed to it. No, I don't know if I've. I don't believe I have been. As far as I know. Yeah.

Speaker 1

And then are there any challenges that you face with regards to addressing vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

Yeah, it would be really-- it is hard to evaluate dependencies fully because you can tell them my answer for-- looking at whether or not something's well maintained, absent of

that was like looking at what dependencies they use and like what are the, are those packages all well maintained and like going through that whole process. It would be really nice if we had some tooling set up that would help alert these vulnerabilities as they happen and through the whole, and then also like telling us what's all been installed.

I think that that's called the Software Bill of Materials. I think the PSF's security in residence is working on that. And so I'm really excited to see that be implemented to a level where I can go ahead and start using it other places. Or if it is, actually, I should go and look. Yeah.

Speaker 1

OK. And opposite to that, what factors help you address vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

What's helped me address vulnerabilities in my project? I mean, the Dependabot tooling and GitHub alerting to security issues, that's extremely helpful. I think that's probably my primary way of finding explicit vulnerabilities in dependencies. It's the large supply chain ones. Those are the ones I find out through my social network. Off the top of my head, those are my two answers for now.

Speaker 1

And what recommendations do you have for open source software dependence management to mitigate supply chain attacks for people who are using this dependently? Do you have any recommendations on what projects maybe they should use in their project?

Speaker 2

The Django project is 1 I would, I think is worth. So any project that has someone who's paid to work or maintain it that has a robust security reporting or security guidelines reporting process and vulnerability disclosure, those are worthwhile. And I don't want to say trusted, but those are robust and well-maintained that you should feel confident in. Yeah, I think anywhere where we can, where a package that has someone being funded to do this really difficult work is probably a place where you can rely on it. I don't know if I have recommendations in other ways of like how to handle this. Like this isn't, Security work isn't my area of focus or specialty. It's more of by necessity. So I would defer to several other experts or people that I know do this work.

Speaker 1

All right. Anything else you might want to add?

Speaker 2

No, well, I'm excited about that a lot of this is getting more attention and that I think there's going to be some new developments and I'm cautiously optimistic about like that things are going to significantly improve. I'm not, I don't have like this pessimistic outlook on our field of, hey, this is all going to become unmaintainable. And I think there are really smart people that are really well incentivized to fix or help improve things. I don't want to say fix things because it's not broken entirely. That's all I got.

Speaker 1

Thank you so much for taking your time to be part of the interview.

00:32:06 Speaker 2

Welcome. Thank you.